

THE SHIFTING SECURITY CALCULOUS OF THE GCC STATES IN A CHANGING WEST ASIA

Maleeha Jamil

PhD Research Scholar, Department of Political Science
Jamia Millia Islamia
maleehajameel938@gmail.com

Abstract

The present paper is an attempt to understand the shifting security calculus of the Gulf Cooperation Council member states following the Arab Spring events, 2011. The organisation of six Persian Gulf was established amidst the Iran-Iraq war in 1980s that threatened their regime stability. It was a collective attempt to protect their shared interests and ensure security of member states from external domination. However, since its establishment the GCC states had majorly relied on external powers for managing the security challenges in an unstable and volatile West Asian region. The emerging challenges at West Asian region due to shifting geopolitical dynamics has aggravated security concerns for the GCC states. The sectarianism strife, rise of militant Islamism, Iran's links with Hezbollah and backing to Houthis in Yemen, Palestine-Israel conflicts have collectively contributed for security concerns among the states in the region. The Arab Spring events had posed new and daunting threats for the GCC states. The declining presence of America as a security provider, increasing role of Russia and China. These events had made GCC to rethink over their security calculus, and to architect new policies to cater to the prevailing security challenges within its framework of integrative institutionalisation.

Keywords: West Asia, Security calculus, geopolitics, Arab Spring, GCC states.

The security threats had remained a central concern for the GCC states since its establishment in 1981. The Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) is an integration of six Persian Gulf states, Bahrain, Kuwait, Qatar, Oman, Saudi Arabia, and UAE, established amidst the emerging security concerns among the gulf states due to the hegemonic war fought between Iran-Iraq in 1980s. The rise of Reza Pahlavi Shah's revolutionary regime

in Iran with expansionist intents in 1970s, and the subsequent outbreak of Iran-Iraq war in September 1980 threatened the existence of monarchical regimes in the Gulf states. The idea of establishing a common platform for securing the shared interest of Persian Gulf states was on the table of discussion, with official dialogue initiating in 1980. The first official summit of GCC was held on May 25, 1981 where the leaders of six states discussed ways to strengthen their relationships while collectively protecting their shared interests and ensuring security of member states from external domination.

The present paper aims to study the evolving security narratives of the GCC states the restructuring of their security calculus over the years amidst the challenges emerging at the wider West Asian region. The WANA states remain in a continuous state of instability and volatility, due to the geopolitical shifts, security challenges emerging from the regional conflicts. The sectarianism strife, rise of militant Islamism, Iran's links with Hezbollah and backing to Houthis in Yemen, Palestine-Israel conflicts have collectively contributed to the security concerns among the states in the region. The Arab Spring events had posed new and daunting threats to the West Asian states, specifically GCC states. The toppling of decades old regimes of Ben Ali, Hosni Mubarak, Qadhafi and Ali Abdel Saleh threatened the regime security of the Gulf monarchies. The increasing instabilities amidst the geopolitical shifts, with the change in power matrix, has made the GCC states to rethink over their security structures. In order to better understand the shifting dynamics of security narratives of the GCC states, the paper first delves onto the theoretical underpinnings of the term 'security' in the context of gulf security studies, the wider perception of threats, distinguished as external and internal threats. Then, the paper will focus on the apparent shifts in the security narratives of the GCC states, from national security to a conflation of national and regime security, since the Arab Spring events of 2011. Subsequently, the paper will analyse the impact of shifts at the regional level that is impacting the security calculus of the GCC states with a change in posture of the players in the GCC security framework, from a declining role of America to the emergence of other powers, like Russia and China. The paper attempts to understand the restructuring of GCC's states security policies amidst the regional geopolitical situation and how GCC states have cater to the prevailing security challenges within its framework of integrative institutionalisation.

Defining ‘Security’ in the context of Gulf Security Studies

While defining the nature of security for the GCC states, the focus has been on traditional narrow aspects of security, that is national and international security, where state is the key referent object of security (Andreas Kreig, 2017, p.44). Though security could not be limited to military threats or securitising the borders, Barry Buzan differentiates among five types of threats; military threats, economic, societal, ecological and political threats. For Buzan, security is an underdeveloped concept, ambiguous, contested and elastic in its meaning (Bary Buzan, 2017, p.4). While Alexander Wendt describes, ‘security as what actors makes of it’ (Alexander Wendt, 1992, p.393) The idea of security in West Asian Security studies, particularly the gulf focuses on ‘limiting external threats to the sovereignty and territorial integrity of the state, while at the same ensuring the survival of the regime internally’ (Andreas Kreig, p.48). The local discourse on gulf security studies in the post-Arab Spring period has witnessed a conflation of “regime security” with “national security”. In view of Ulrichsen, the concept of domestic/ internal and regional/external security seems to overlap post-2011 in the context of gulf security studies. The focus of the present study will be on interpreting security as a state-centric concept for the GCC states, where the security policies stresses on threats to state and regime security.

External and Internal Threats to the GCC states’ Security: The Persian Gulf remains an extremely volatile subregion in West Asia with multitude of intertwining internal and external threats to the security of the member states (Kristian Coates Ulrichsen, 2009). Bianco define, the term ‘threat’ in context of security studies on the gulf states, as the dangers that impede or weaken the state structures and regimes (Cinzia Bianco, 2018, p.1). The threats in security studies are basically distinguished as external and internal threats. In context of gulf security studies, the external threats are concerned with the state security while internal ones are linked to regime stability. Historically, the GCC states are constantly faced with two external threats, that is Iran and Iraq while ideological threats, internally and externally emerging mainly from Iraq’s ‘pan-Arabism’ and Iran’s ‘Khomeinism’ had triggered the security concerns for the GCC states.

Ulrichsen adopts a constructivist approach in explaining threats perception of the gulf states. He implies that not only the stability of the GCC states

is not only threatened by 'hard-security', rather they are posed with 'soft-security' or the ideological challenges as well. Mohammad Ayoob points at the absence of a democratic procedure in the GCC states, has heightened the concerns of gulf rulers who majorly perceives threats through the lens of 'regime survival' (Cinzia Bianco, 2018, p.2). The ideological threats are considered highly threatening to the survivability of monarchical regimes in the GCC states since the pro-democracy protests sweeping the Arab world, overthrowing the decades old regimes in Tunisia, Egypt, Libya, and Yemen.

1) The Shifting Security Narratives of the GCC states:

GCC states have majorly relied on external powers to manage their security challenges. Britain remained the sole security provider for the gulf states until its withdrawal in 1971. Britain's withdrawal from gulf states in 1970s, shifted the balance of power and security towards America.

The multitude of worrying events in late 1970s gave an added impetus to a more active involvement of America in the security calculus of the gulf region. The Carter doctrine in 1980s ultimately brought the Arab gulf states under the security umbrella of United States. The doctrine stated, 'any attempt by any outside power on the Persian Gulf region, will be regarded as an assault on the vital interests of the United States and such an assault will be repelled by any means necessary, including military force' (Hal Brands, Steven A. Cook, and Kenneth M. Pollack, 2019).

The fall of Reza Pahlavi Shah's regime in Iran, the Islamic Revolution and the subsequent outbreak of the Iran-Iraq war in 1980s exacerbated the security concerns of the gulf states. The gulf states were extremely shocked over the fall of a powerful monarch in Iran. The rise of Shi'ite protests in Saudi Arabia, Bahrain and an expansionist regime in Iran intending to lead the Arab states threatened the regime survivability of the other gulf states. The remaining six gulf states amidst the uncertain situation in the region due to the ongoing Iran-Iraq war, unanimously agreed for the establishment of a Cooperation Council in February 1981. Bahrain, Qatar, Kuwait, Oman, Saudi Arabia and UAE signed the final charter and officially established the Cooperation Council for the Arab Gulf States of the Gulf or the Gulf Cooperation Council on 25 May, 1981. GCC was established as an integrated and collective effort for confronting the economic, social, political and security challenges of the

member states. However it was in 1983 when security issues found a place among the discussions of the Cooperation Council. The member-states had their first joint military exercise titled as 'Peninsula Shield' in 1984. The Council also approved the developed of a Gulf rapid deployment force at the fifth summit meeting, indicating that an attack on any member states would be considered as an attack on all. However the intensifying Iran-Iraq war in the latter half of 1980s, made it obvious for the GCC member states that none of these options could provide comprehensive security for ensuring regional stability. It was only United States that GCC states could rely on for military assistance, leading to the establishment of Central Command (CENTCOM) that replaced Carter's Rapid Deployment Force.

America increased its military presence in subsequent years in the Gulf region to protect its energy and security interests, and to buffer against the threats from Iran and Iraq. When Iraq invaded Kuwait in 1990s, Saudi turned to United States for military assistance, that was quick to respond with deploying more than 600,000 troops. The American military power was the closest viable option available to defend the Kingdom and to evict Iraqi forces from Kuwait. With the successful destruction of Iraq's military capabilities, United States emerged as the most viable powerful regional actor in the Gulf. It positioned itself as the security guarantor of the GCC states, developing an 'oil-for-security arrangement' (Md, Mudassir Quamar, 2023). However, instead of adopting a comprehensive security arrangement for the bloc, the GCC member states had integrated under the US security umbrella or any other extra-regional power for defense purposes on a bilateral basis. The bilateral defence alliance system developed in the aftermath of Kuwait's invasion, formed the basis of the external security relations of the GCC states (Victar Gervais, 2017, p.34). However, the changing regional dynamics at the turn of the century, with the launching of war on terror, the American invasion of Iraq, Saddam Hussain being ousted from power, subsequently Iraq getting weaker and Iran emerging as a dominant player in the region brought new security concerns for the GCC states. United States war on Iraq strengthened the role of non-state actors, with Iran's emerging support for groups like Hezbollah and Hamas challenging the regional status quo. The American invasion of Iraq increased the sectarian tensions in the region, the Shia-Sunni tensions was another new source of instability and conflict. It further

threatened America's ability to guarantee regional security, a concern for the GCC member states that had majorly relied on America for security purposes. The shifts in America's domestic policies, with the election of President Barack Obama in 2008 was a turning point for its role in the Gulf region, witnessing a significant reconfiguration in its policies towards the GCC states. The policy shifts intensified with the Arab Spring events, ushering an era of uncertainty and instability for the GCC states and wider West Asian region. The Arab Uprising signalled the beginning of a transformative phase, posing serious threats to the stability and security of the West Asian states.

The pro-democracy uprisings, resulted in a widespread revolutionary wave that ended the decades of authoritarian ruling in Tunisia, Egypt, Libya and Yemen. In view of Bianco, 'the region found itself on the brink of transition of political and economic power to new actors and new regimes, representing an alternative to the existing authoritarian regime' (Cinzia Bianco, 2024, p.1). The GCC monarchies, considered as the island of stability were heavily affected by these events, exacerbating the domestic and regional security concerns. They inspired significant opposition to ruling regimes in GCC member states of Oman, Kuwait, Bahrain and Saudi's Eastern province. The gulf monarchies cracked down on the protests either through economic handouts or military repression. The GCC states were concerned over the security of their regimes. The taking down of authoritarian regimes by popular protest threatened their regime survivability.

The revolutionary protests resulted in a power vacuum, creating the space for the rise of non-state actors, the Islamist factions affiliated to Muslim Brotherhood, Houthis in Yemen, Hezbollah backed by Iraq. The uprisings turned into an ongoing civil war in Syria, with Russia and Iran extending support to Bashar al-Assad's regime, creating vacuum for the rise militias and pro-Shiite groups. The rise of Jihadist terrorist group, Deash in Iraq and Syria that launched a series of terrorist attacks on Saudi Arabia in 2014, threatened the Arab Gulf states. The emerging strengths of rebel group, Houthis in Yemen bordering Saudi to the north, was another security concern for the GCC states. The Houthis backed by Iran, had targeted Saudi and UAE territories, with missiles and drones. Another noticeable trend was the intensification of sectarian strife, the decades old rivalry between Sunni Arab monarchies and the Shiite Iran. The Sunni ruling regimes in Saudi and Bahrain had prioritised balancing

against their rebellious Shia populations and the proximate groups linked to Tehran (Cinzia Bianco, 2018, p.2). Iran's support for these militant groups, Hezbollah, Houthis and Assad's regime in Syria boosted their power, exacerbating the security concerns among the gulf states.

With the repositioning of United States role in the West Asian region post-2011 events, developed a realisation among the GCC states that America is losing interest as their guarantor of security, causing a fundamental rethinking among the GCC states over their security calculus. And a reassessing of their security perceptions and policies domestically and regionally. The geopolitical shifts, in view of Cinzia Bianco, 'caused a transformation of role of GCC states from security consumers to security producers, leverage their political networks and vast financial resources, to become the architects of the post-2011 regional order' (Cinzia Bianco, 2024, p.2). America's resetting of relations with GCC states, deepened Russian and China's strategic influence, as the new 'non-western' entrants in the region. Russia increasingly presented itself as a security provider willing to support the regional regimes without interfering in their internal affairs (Roland Dannreuther, 2021, p.127).

The United States withdrawal from Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA) in 2018 was another game-changing event. JCPOA was an attempt to curb Iran's nuclear capabilities and to paving the way for normalisation of Iran's role in the region. Trump's decision to pull out from JCPOA, increased the regional conflicts, with Iran launching low-intensity attacks against Saudi Arabia and UAE. The attacks in 2019 hit several oil tankers of Saudi Arabia and critical infrastructures of ARAMCO. America refrained from responding, demonstrating its retrenchment as security provider for the GCC states. GCC monarchies after 2019 reassessed their security agendas and opened a new phase in their regional policies, characterised by consolidation and diplomatic manoeuvre, embracing a strategic pause to escalation (Cinzia Bianco, 2024, p.3). GCC states deepened their defence, trade and technology relations with China and Russia, United Kingdom, and France. Joe Biden's election to the office of President in 2020 promised resetting the relations with gulf, adopting a policy of recalibration. The series of crisis in the region, and the recent outbreak of the war in Gaza with a risk of regional escalation had catalysed the regional stability. The war has not only threatened the national security but has created an unavoidable

dilemma for the GCC states. The Gaza war occurred at a time when the GCC monarchies had agreed for normalising relations with Israel backed by United States, sidelining the Palestine issue. However, the war once again brought the Palestine issue at the center of the Arab politics, pausing the normalisation deals, pressurising the GCC monarchies to take a strong diplomatic position against Israel, and incorporate the Palestinian component in the normalisation deals (Cinzia Bianco and Camille Lans, 2024).

2) Strategic Cohesion of Gulf Cooperation Council in the realm of security

The instable West Asian region, whether its civil war in Syria, threats from Yemen and Iraq, or the regional escalation of the ongoing war in Gaza, with the region getting closer to a wider conflict following Iran's attack on Israel, GCC states sees nothing but trouble all around its borders. Since the Britain withdrawal from the gulf region in 1971, America has remained a crucial security guarantor for the gulf states, the role was strengthened with the emerging security concerns following the Iran-Iraq war in 1980s. The Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) was established in 1981 as an organisations to provide security and defense of the member state amidst the Iran-Iraq. However, GCC has largely remained an integrative institutional forum for coordinating policies in multitude of realms among the member states. In forty-two years of its working, the bloc has failed to integrate their policies into a successful military alliance. The internal crisis within the GCC bloc and diverging perceptions of security and threats had consistently hindered coordinated security efforts in dealing with the regional instabilities. While United Arab Emirates (UAE), Bahrain and Saudi Arabia favour a 'collective security process to address the member-states security needs', the small states, Kuwait, Qatar and Oman are more inclined towards 'a cooperative security model that will account for their concerns and regional interests' (Sanam Vakil, 2022).

The limitations of GCC's coordinated efforts and self-reliance in the realm of security are embedded in the inadequate foreign decision making authority and a culture of dependence. The Petrodollar revolution in the 1970s had developed a rent-seeking behaviour and culture of dependence for defending its territories among the gulf monarchies. The monarchies had relied majorly on extra-regional powers for ensuring the

‘state security’. The GCC states relied on America as a security-guarantor for securing its territorial sovereignty, whether from regional rivals, Iran and Iraq, or any other threat emerging from regional conflicts. In view of Gresh, ‘the domestic police had been designed intently to maintain monarchy’s power and control over society, lacking capabilities to defend the territories in the event of an external attack’ (Geoffrey F. Gresh, 2015, p.26). The GCC states despite spending billions on military expenses and training, with the exception of UAE, possess almost no ability to sustain an external military attack or conflict on their own.

The Cooperation Council’s initiative towards a joint military unit, Peninsula Shield Force, created in 1984, had weakened over the time due to diverging national interest, competition and suspicion among the member states. For this reason, the member states had relied on security assistance from the United States. Jean-Loup Samaan points at, ‘the reluctance among the GCC states has restricted the transformation of political linkages to military ones’ (Jean-Loup Samaan, 2024). The GCC monarchies are imposed with the twin challenges of external and internal threats in the post-Arab Spring period. The efforts towards a coordinated union had been repeatedly stymied by small gulf that had raised contention over Saudi’s weightage in the bloc. The GCC’s working was critically damaged during the Gulf rift, 2014 and the Qatar Crisis, 2017-21. Saudi, UAE and Bahrain’s suspicion of Doha’s linkage with Political Islamist groups such as the Muslim Brotherhood and diplomatic ties with Iran resulted in an economic and diplomatic blockade on Qatar. The blockade was lifted in 2021 with the al-Ula agreement, but it critically hindered the bloc’s coordinated efforts in the realm of security. The outbreak of Gaza war in October 2023 had posed another dangerous security challenge for the GCC states. The escalation of the war, with Houthis attacking against the international shipping in the Red Sea aggravated the concerns of Saudi’s maritime security. However, the moderated stance of GCC states on the Gaza war, explains Saudi’s act of securing its diplomatic and national security interests while balancing its diplomatic position on the Palestinian cause (Cinzia Bianco and Camille Lans, 2024).

The instabilities amidst the geopolitical shifts, with the change in power matrix, has made the GCC states to rethink over their security structures. The vacuum created by less assertive western power, provides an

opportunity for the GCC states to work in the direction of regional stability, as the security providers. In the direction of comprehensive regional security arrangement, the GCC states for the first time announced its 'Vision for Regional Security' in December, 2024. The strategic objective of the vision as stated in the document, 'seek to maintain regional security, stability of the countries of the region and prosperity of their people, ensuring security of the energy supplies and oil markets, fostering maritime security, as well as enhancing international security and peace' (Gulf Cooperation Council Vision for Regional Security, 2024). The explicit mention of the ongoing crisis in Gaza, highlights the collective role of the GCC in resolving the Israel-Palestine conflict and maintaining regional stability and peace.

References:

- Brands, H., Cook, S., & Pollack, K. M. (2019, December 13). *Rip the Carter Doctrine, 1980-2019*. Retrieved April 15, 2024, from Foreign Policy: <https://foreignpolicy.com/2019/12/15/carter-doctrine-rip-donald-trump-mideast-oil-big-think/>
- Bianco, C. (2020, June 10). The GCC Monarchies: Perceptions of the Iranian Threat amid Shifting Geopolitics. *The International Spectator*, 55(2), 92-107.
- Bianco, C. (2024). *The Gulf Monarchies after the Arab Spring: Threats and Security*. Manchester: Manchester University Press.
- Bianco, C. (2024, January 12). *National interests and regional turmoil: The Gulf states' view on Gaza and the Red Sea*. Retrieved 2024 April, from European Council on Foreign Relations: <https://ecfr.eu/article/national-interests-and-regional-turmoil-the-gulf-states-view-on-gaza-and-the-red-sea/>
- Cafiero, G., & Khalid al-Jaber. (2020, June 04). *GCC States' Security As the Council Turns into A Failed Institution*. Retrieved April 2024, from Gulf International Forum: <https://gulffif.org/gcc-states-security-as-the-councils-turns-into-a-failed-institution/>
- Ehteshami, A. (2013). *Dynamics of Change in the Persian Gulf*. London: Routledge.
- Gresh, G. F. (2015). *Gulf Security and the U.S. Military: Regime Survival and the Politics of Basing*. California: Stanford University Press.
- Kamrawa, M. (Ed.). (2011). *International Politics of the Persian Gulf*. Syracuse: Syracuse University Press.

- Kechichian, J. A. (1985, October). The Gulf Cooperation Council: Search for Security. *Third World Quarterly*, 7(4), 853-881.
- Miller, R. (2016). *Desert Kingdoms to Global Powers: The Rise of the Arab Gulf*. London: Yale University Press.
- Macris, J. R. (2010). *The Politics And Security of the Gulf: Anglo-American Hegemony and the Shaping of a Region*. London: Routledge, Taylor and Francis Group.
- Naaz, F. (2001, March). Security in the Persian Gulf. *Strategic Analysis*, 24(12), 2257-2271.
- Pradhan, P. K. (Ed.). (2016). *Geopolitical Shifts in West Asia: Trends and Implication*. New Delhi, India: Pentagon Press.
- Quamar, M. M. (2023, July 10). *A new dynamism in foreign policy of GCC States*. Retrieved 2024 May , from Financial Express: <https://www.financialexpress.com/world-news/a-new-dynamism-in-foreign-policy-of-gcc-states/3162654/>
- Rouholla K. Ramazani, J. A. (1988). *The Gulf Cooperation Council: Record and Analysis*. Charlottesville: University Press of Virginia.
- Samaan, J.-L. (2024, May 9). *The GCC's Joint Security Vision: Reading Between the Lines*. Retrieved May 2024, from Gulf International Forum: <https://gulrif.org/the-gccs-joint-security-vision-reading-between-the-lines/>
- Sandwick, J. A. (Ed.). (1987). *The Gulf Cooperation Council: Moderation and Stability in an Interdependent World ” Excerpt From The Gulf Cooperation Council: Moderation and Stability in an Interdependent World*. New York: Routledge.
- Stephens, M. (2015, March 02). *A big rethink: Security in the GCC*. Retrieved April 13, 2024, from Al-Jazeera: <https://www.aljazeera.com/opinions/2015/3/2/a-big-rethink-security-in-the-gcc>
- Tareq Y. Ismael, J. S. (2011). *Government and Politics of the Contemporary Middle East: Continuity and Change*. London: Routledge.
- Ulrichsen, K. C. (2015, May 8). *The Political Economy of Arab Gulf States*. James A. Baker III Institute For Public Policy, Rice University.
- Ulrichsen, K. C. (2023, October 18). *Saudi plans to ‘de-risk’ region have taken a hit with Gaza violence – but hitting pause on normalisation with Israel will buy kingdom time*. Retrieved 2023 Novemebr, from The Conversation: <https://theconversation.com/saudi-plans-to-de-risk-region-have-taken-a-hit-with-gaza-violence-but-hitting-pause-on-normalization-with-israel-will-buy-kingdom-time-215657>

The Shifting Security Calculous of the GCC States ... – Jamil

Vakil, S. (2022, November 30). *Understanding the GCC Collective Security Mindset*. Retrieved April 15, 2024, from Chatham House: <https://kalam.chathamhouse.org/articles/understanding-the-gcc-collective-security-mindset/>

Wendt, A. (1992). Anarchy is What States Makes of It: The Social Construction of Power Politics. *International Organization*, 46(2), 391-425.

(2024). *Gulf Cooperation Council Vision for Regional Security*. The Cooperation Council for the Arab States of the Gulf Secretariat - General.

Ulrichsen, K. C. (2009, June). Internal and External Security in the Arab Gulf States. *Middle East Policy*, XVI(2), 39-58.